

Antimicrobial agents from nematode-associated ascomycetes isolated
from *Heterodera filipjevi*

Der Fakultät für Lebenswissenschaften
der Technischen Universität Carolo-Wilhelmina zu Braunschweig

zur Erlangung des Grades eines
Doktors der Naturwissenschaften
(Dr. rer. nat.)
eingereichte

D i s s e r t a t i o n

Kumulative Arbeit

von Jan-Peer Wennrich

aus Braunschweig

1. Referent: Prof. Dr. Marc Stadler
2. Referent: Prof. Dr. Michael Steinert
eingereicht am:
mündliche Prüfung (Disputation) am:

Vorveröffentlichungen der Dissertation

Teilergebnisse aus dieser Arbeit wurden mit Genehmigung der Fakultät für Lebenswissenschaften, vertreten durch den Mentor der Arbeit, in folgenden Beiträgen vorab veröffentlicht:

List of Publications

- I Wennrich J-P, Sepanian E, Ebada SS, Llanos-Lopez NA, Ashrafi S, Maier W, Kurtán T, Stadler M (2023) Bioactive naphtho- α -pyranones from two endophytic fungi of the genus *Polyphilus*. *Antibiotics* 12(8):1273. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antibiotics12081273>.
- II Wennrich J-P, Ebada SS, Sepanian E, Holzenkamp C, Khalid SJ, Schrey H, Maier W, Mándi A, Kurtán T, Ashrafi S, Stadler M (2024) Omnipolyphilins A and B: Chlorinated cyclotrapeptides and naphtho- α -pyranones from the plant nematode-derived fungus *Polyphilus sieberi*. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry* 72(13):6998–7009. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jafc.4c00572>.
- III Holzenkamp C, Wennrich J-P, Muema JM, Ashrafi S, Maier W, Stadler M, Ebada SS (2024) Laburnicotides A–F: Acyclic N-acetyl oligopeptides from the nematode-cyst-associated fungus *Laburnicola nematophila*. *ACS Omega* 9(19):21658–21667. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.4c02719>.
- IV Wennrich J-P, Holzenkamp C, Ashrafi S, Maier W, Wang H, Ibrahim MAA, Ebada SS, Stadler M (2024) Laburnicolamine: A rare penillic acid congener from the nematode cyst-associated fungus *Laburnicola nematophila*. *Chemistry & Biodiversity* 202401152:1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cbdv.202401152>.
- V Wennrich J-P, Holzenkamp C, Kolařík M, Maier W, Mándi A, Kurtán T, Ashrafi S, Ebada SS, Stadler M (2024) Dactylfungins and tetralones: Bioactive metabolites from a nematode-associated *Laburnicola nematophila*. *Journal of Natural Products*. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jnatprod.4c00623>.
- VI Ashrafi S, Wennrich J-P, Becker Y, Maciá-Vicente JG, Brißke-Rode A, Daub M, Thünen T, Dababat D, Finckh M, Stadler M, Maier W (2023) *Polydomus karssenii* gen. nov. sp. nov. is a dark septate endophyte with a bifunctional lifestyle parasitising eggs of plant parasitic cyst nematodes (*Heterodera* spp.). *IMA Fungus* 14(1):6. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43008-023-00113-w>.

List of poster presentations

Wennrich J-P, Surup F, Llanos-López NA, Helaly SE, Ashrafi S, Maier W, Stadler M. **(2022)** Screening for biologically active agents from nematode-associated fungi. American Society of Pharmacognosy Annual Meeting Natural Product Solutions to Global Challenges, North Charleston, South Carolina, USA

Wennrich J-P, Surup F, Ebada SS, Llanos-López NA, Helaly SE, Ashrafi S, Maier W, Stadler M. **(2023)** Discovery of new anti-infectives in nematode-associated fungi. International Helmholtz Drug Discovery Conference, Braunschweig, Germany

Wennrich J-P, Sepanian E, Ebada SS, Llanos-López NA, Helaly SE, Ashrafi S, Maier W, Stadler M. **(2023)** Metabolic exploration of the genus *Polyphilus*. Westerdijk Spring Symposium Fungal Evolution, Amsterdam, Netherlands

Wennrich J-P, Surup F, Ebada SS, Caren H, Sepanian E, Llanos-López NA, Ashrafi S, Maier W, Stadler M **(2024)** New bioactive secondary metabolites from nematode-associated fungi. 36th Irsee Natural Product Symposium, Irsee, Germany

Declaration of Contribution to the publications

- I** Conceptualization: JPW, SSE and MS; culture characterisation: SA and WM; methodology and investigation: JPW, ES and NAL-L; data curation and interpretation: JPW, SSE and TK; structure elucidation: SSE and TK; visualization: JPW and SSE; writing—original draft preparation: JPW and SSE; writing—review and editing: all authors. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.
- II** Conceptualization: JPW, SSE, MS; strain isolation and characterisation: SA, WM; methodology and investigation: JPW, ES, CH, SJK, HS; data curation and interpretation: JPW, SSE, AM, TK, HS; structure elucidation: SSE and TK; visualization: JPW, SSE; writing-original draft preparation: JPW, SSE; writing-review and editing: All authors read and approved the final manuscript.
- III** Conceptualization: JPW, SSE, MS; strain isolation and characterisation: SA, WM; methodology and investigation: CH, JPW, JM; data curation and interpretation: CH, JPW, SSE; structure elucidation: SSE; antiviral assay: JM; visualization: CH, JPW, SSE; writing-original draft preparation: CH, JPW, SSE; writing-review and editing: All authors read and approved the final manuscript.
- IV** Conceptualization: JPW, MS; fungal isolation and identification: SA, WM; methodology: CH, JPW; formal analysis: CH, JPW, SSE; data curation and structure elucidation: SSE and HW; TDDFT-ECD: MAAI; nematicidal activity: CH, JPW; writing—original draft preparation: CH, JPW, SSE; writing—review and editing: SSE, MS; project administration: MS; funding acquisition: MS. All authors have read and agreed on the published version of the manuscript.
- V** Conceptualization: JPW, SSE, MS; strain isolation and characterisation: SA, WM; methodology and investigation: JPW, CH, MK; data curation and interpretation: JPW, SSE, AM, TK; structure elucidation: SSE and TK; visualization: JPW, SSE; writing-original draft preparation: JPW, SSE; writing-review and editing: All authors read and approved the final manuscript.
- VI** Conceptualization, SA, AD, MS, WM; sampling, SA, TT, MD, AD, JMV; Methodology and analyses, SA, ABR, JPW; fungal isolation: SA, JMV; data curation SA, TT; visualisation: SA, YB; writing—original draft preparation: SA, JPW; writing—review and editing: All authors; All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Acknowledgements

Reflecting on the whirlwind of the past 4.5 years, it feels like time has flown by in the blink of an eye. First and foremost, I would like to thank my supervisor Marc Stadler, for not just giving me the chance to pursue my PhD in your department Microbial Drugs (MWIS) at the HZI but also for letting me take the lead on my projects. Your guidance has been invaluable, not just in professional matters but in personal challenges as well. Your willingness to listen and your support have opened doors for me to explore the world and meet incredible people. Marc, I can't thank you enough for your kindness and unwavering support which I will never forget.

I thank Prof. Dr. Michael Steinert for agreeing to be the second reviewer of this thesis. I am grateful for Prof. Dr. Ludger Beerhues to take the chair of the oral defence. Prof. Dr. Rainer Krull and Dr. Wolfgang Maier are thanked for their guidance in the thesis committee.

I'm also incredibly thankful to my colleagues and friends, Dr. Sherif S. Ebada and Dr. Frank Surup. Your enthusiasm for chemistry was contagious and crucial in the success of our publications. The knowledge and insights you shared have been important to my learning and understanding of structure elucidation.

Dr. Samad Ashrafi, Dr. Birthe Sandargo, Dr. Hedda Schrey, Dr. Miriam Große, Dr. Yasmina Marin-Felix and Silke Reinecke your expertise and guidance across various topics have always been incredibly helpful and insightful. I really appreciate the time you've taken to assist me.

To my office mates and dear friends, Sebastian and Esteban, thanks for the enriching conversations and fun times. My students, Caren, Ellen, and Janette, your contributions have been significant, and I appreciate all your hard work. And to all my co-authors, your collaboration has been a pillar of our success.

I would like to thank all current and former member of MWIS: Aileen, Andrew, Anke, Axel, Birthe, Blondelle, Christel, Christiane, Christin, Christopher, Dana, Daniela, Esther S., Esther Sch., Hao, Hedda, Khadija, Kerstin, Kevin, Javariya, Lilly, Majorie, Manuela, Maria, Max, Nadine, Özge, Steffen, Steffi, Tanja, Tian, Rita, Wera, Winnie and Yen – if I've missed mentioning anyone, know that it's only because we've been such a large, dynamic group over the years.

Despite the challenges thrown our way by the pandemic, including moving to a new building, we've managed to navigate through these times effectively, making the best of our circumstances.

Lastly, I cannot overlook the foundational support in my life - Jan, Nikita, Tobi, and Maya, who played a pivotal role in my decision to start this PhD journey. To my family, friends, and especially my partner, Adela, your encouragement has been my strength. Here's to hoping for your continued support for me and our son, Arthur.

This journey has been nothing short of amazing, thanks to each one of you. Your support, in many ways, has made all the difference.

- To all of you, my sincere and deepest gratitude -

Abbreviations

BRFT	brown rice fermentation
CCN	cereal cyst nematode
CD	circular dichroism
CN	cyst nematode
COPS	Department of “Compound Profiling and Screening” at HZI
DAD	diode array detection
DCM	dichloromethane
DSM	designation of strain accession numbers of German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures (DSMZ), Braunschweig, Germany
ECD	electronic circular dichroism
ESI	electrospray ionization
FA	formic acid
FDA	food and drug administration
HMBC	heteronuclear multiple-bond correlation spectroscopy
HPLC	high performance liquid chromatography
HRMS	high resolution mass spectrometry
HSQC	heteronuclear single-quantum correlation spectroscopy
HZI	Helmholtz Centre for Infection Research GmbH
ITS	internal transcribed spacer region of the ribosomal DNA
MHB	Mueller Hinton Broth
MIC	minimal inhibitory concentration
MPLC	medium pressure liquid chromatography
MRSA	methicillin-resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
MS	mass spectrometry
NMR	nuclear magnetic resonance
NP	normal phase
NRPS	nonribosomal peptide synthetase
PKS	polyketide synthase
PPN	plant parasitic nematode
ROESY	rotating frame nuclear Overhauser effect spectroscopy
RP	reversed phase
TDDFT	time-dependent density functional theory
TOCSY	total correlation spectroscopy
WHO	World Health Organisation
WOFT	whole oat fermentation
ZBIO	Department of “Cell Biology” at HZI

Summary

Fungi play an essential role in human civilization and natural ecosystems through their multifaceted roles. Historically, humans have harnessed fungi for food production, medicine, agriculture, and biotechnology. In medicine, fungi have led to the discovery of crucial drugs such as penicillin, cephalosporin, cyclosporine A, and statins, revolutionizing medical treatments and significantly improving public health. However, the rise of antibiotic resistance has become a critical global challenge, threatening the effectiveness of existing drugs and underscoring the urgent need for new molecules to combat antibiotic-resistant organisms.

This study focuses on the potential of nematophagous fungi, isolated from the eggs of the cereal cyst nematode *Heterodera filipjevi* and related species from various regions, to discover compounds with unique antimicrobial properties. The selected methodology included screening in various media, extraction, and isolation of secondary metabolites using classical chromatographic methods. Structure elucidation was performed with a combination of MS, UV, ECD, and 1D and 2D NMR measurements, along with derivatization reactions like Marfey's or Mosher method in special cases. The isolated metabolites were then biologically characterised against a panel of selected Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, fungi, *Caenorhabditis elegans* and mammalian cell lines.

The results revealed several compounds with significant antimicrobial efficacy, highlighting their potential application within different fields. In particular, the study discusses the feasibility of using these fungi as biocontrol agents against globally relevant agricultural pathogens, particularly plant parasitic nematodes. This represents an environmentally friendly alternative to traditional nematicides, which are prohibited in the majority of countries due to their toxicity on soil microorganisms, vertebrates, and humans.

Notably, the genus *Polyphilus* was found to produce the mycotoxins talaroderxine C and D, which have a dominant effect on *Staphylococcus aureus* biofilms, along with other intriguing metabolites. *Laburnicola nematophila* produced the highly antifungal dactylfungins, effective against azole-resistant *Aspergillus fumigatus*. Preliminary findings for *L. nematophila* and

Polydomus karssenii suggest that many secondary metabolites remain undiscovered and uncharacterised for these taxa, indicating the need for future research.

In conclusion, this research highlights the potential of fungi to produce a wide array of natural products with diverse or hidden biological properties. It also emphasizes the need to study fungi comprehensively before developing them into biocontrol agents. The study's findings open new avenues for sustainable agriculture and drug discovery, addressing pressing global challenges such as antibiotic resistance and food security.

1. Introduction

Fungi represent a diverse kingdom of organisms that have become deeply integrated into the human civilization as well as natural ecosystems through their multifaceted roles and practical applications. Fungi have significantly impacted essential ecological processes, such as nutrient cycling. They form complex relationships with a diverse range of organisms, including plants. These relationships can range from mutualism and other forms of symbioses [Carroll, 1988; Fisher et al., 2012; Liu et al., 2020]. Historically, humans have utilized fungi for food, medicine, and biotechnological processes, underscoring their importance in agriculture and industry [Hyde et al., 2019]. Archaeological evidence indicates that humans have been utilising fungi for food preparation and preservation since the Neolithic era. This is evidenced by the discovery of yeast and molds in archaeological sites dating back to this period [Li et al., 2016]. One of the oldest and most culturally significant uses of fungi is evident in the domestication of the brewing yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, a cornerstone in the production of bread, beer, and wine since ancient civilizations [Replansky et al., 2008].

In medicine, fungi have been revolutionary, notably through the rediscovery of penicillin (Fig. 1) from *Penicillium rubens* by Alexander Fleming in 1928, which marked a milestone in modern medicine. This discovery started the era of antibiotics, known as the “golden age of antibiotic discovery”, transforming once lethal infections into treatable conditions [Fleming, 1929; Houbraken et al., 2011; Bills and Gloer, 2016]. This era catalyzed the development of numerous antimicrobial agents beside other useful drugs. These advancements played a pivotal role in extending human life expectancy and improving quality on a global scale. Additionally, the increasing understanding of pathogens and improved hygienic measures contributed to these improvements [Mohr, 2016]. Despite these advances, antibiotic resistance has become increasingly concerning in recent decades. This has led to the emergence and spread of multidrug-resistant microbes, which caused higher mortality and morbidity [Boucher et al., 2009; Pendleton et al., 2013]. Several factors have contributed to the rapid increase of multidrug-resistant microbes compared to the introduction of new antibiotics to the market. Those include inadequate use of antibiotics in clinics and intensive use in the animal and food industries, as well as the termination of antibiotic research in larger pharmaceutical companies [Kresse et al., 2007;

O'Connell et al., 2013; Bengtsson and Greko, 2014]. Currently, the majority of antibiotics in use are still largely derived from substances first described in the 1950s and 1960s. Examples include tetracyclines and cephalosporins [Davies, 2006]. This phenomenon reduces the clinical efficacy of current drugs, which could ultimately result in a post-antibiotic era treatable infections could once again become lethal. This situation creates a dire need for innovative strategies to identify novel bioactive compounds [O'Connell et al., 2013]. In this context, the exploration of natural products has historically been a productive approach for drug discovery. These substances are derived from natural sources such as plants, bacteria, and fungi. Notably, a significant proportion of antibiotics currently in clinical use are derived from fungal and microbial sources. They include semi-synthetic modifications, and mimics of natural products, underscoring their invaluable contribution to medicinal chemistry [Newman and Cragg, 2020; Miethke et al., 2021].

Important fungal natural products

Amidst the above-mentioned crisis, fungi have emerged as a pivotal source for novel antibiotic leads. They also have other useful applications in modern medicine and agriculture due to their diverse ecological roles and rich metabolic capabilities to produce a variety of natural products [Hyde et al., 2019; Newman and Cragg, 2020].

Natural products are chemical compounds synthesised by living organisms. These compounds are often characteristic of a species, genus, or taxonomic family and are derived from intermediates of primary metabolic pathways [Larsen et al., 2005]. Especially interesting are secondary metabolites. Unlike primary metabolites, which are essential for an organism's growth and development, secondary metabolites play crucial roles in communication, mutualism, environmental adaptation, parasitism, nutrient acquisition, defense, and competition [Krauss and Nies, 2014]. The secondary metabolites have given humanity significant advantages throughout history. This is exemplified by the earlier mentioned β -lactam antibiotic, penicillin G (**1**). The β -lactam antibiotics have bacteriostatic effects and target the biosynthesis of the peptidoglycan in bacterial cell walls during the cell division and are therefore especially effective against gram-positive bacteria. In order to provide a comprehensive overview of the history of fungal drugs, it is necessary to start with the year 1893. In this year mycophenolic acid (**2**) was isolated from

Penicillium brevicompactum as an agent against *Bacillus anthracis*. It was subsequently withdrawn from the market due to its toxic side effects. However, a semisynthetic derivative, mycophenolate mofetil, remains available today as a potent immunosuppressant and highly successful drug [Bentley, 2000]. In addition to the β -lactam antibiotic penicillin G, the cephalosporin family (e.g., cephalosporin C (**3**)) was also discovered from the fungal species *Sarocladium strictum*, which was previously known as *Cephalosporium acremonium* [Bills and Gloer, 2016; García-Estrada and Martín, 2019; Hou et al., 2023]. The isolated cephalosporin C showed only weak antibacterial effects but was used as a template for the development of several generations of modifications. The later semisynthetically produced cephalosporin generations like 3rd (**4**) to 5th (**5**) generation were developed into a broad-spectrum antibiotic with even activity against challenging multi-resistant Gram-positive bacteria, and Gram-negative bacteria [García-Estrada and Martín, 2019; Newman and Cragg, 2020].

Another significant advancement in the field of antibiotics includes the isolation of fusidic acid (**6**) and pleuromutilins (**7**), both of which have made substantial contributions to treating bacterial infections. Fusidic acid, a triterpenoid of the fusidane type, is produced by the strain *Ramularia coccinea* (formerly known as *Fusidium coccineum*). First described in 1962 by Godtfredsen and colleagues, fusidic acid operates by inhibiting bacterial protein synthesis. It achieves this by locking elongation factor-G to the ribosome post-GTP hydrolysis. Fusidic acid demonstrates a narrow spectrum of activity, predominantly targeting Gram-positive bacteria. It is commonly used as a topical agent, particularly for treatment of skin infections [Godtfredsen et al., 1962; Fernandes, 2016]. The discovery of pleuromutilins from *Clitopilus passeckerianus*, formerly known as *Pleurotus passeckerianus*, in the early 1950s marked a significant advancement in antibiotic research from Basidiomycota [Kavanagh et al., 1951]. These compounds exhibited activity against Gram-positive bacteria and mycoplasmas. By binding the centre of the peptidyl transferase, pleuromutilins inhibit protein synthesis, which is exhibiting low resistance development [Paukner and Riedl, 2017; Newman and Cragg, 2020; Mapook et al., 2022]. Semisynthetic derivatives, tiamulin and valnemulin, were introduced for veterinary use in 1979 and 1999, respectively, to treat swine dysentery and enzootic pneumonia [Poulsen et al., 2001]. Interest in pleuromutilins for human medicine resurfaced due to rising β -lactam

resistance. This led to the FDA approval of retapamulin in 2007 for treating bacterial skin infections, and later, lefamulin for community-acquired bacterial pneumonia (CABP) in 2019 [Paukner and Riedl, 2017; Newman and Cragg, 2020; Mapook et al., 2022].

Additionally, the repurposing of certain natural product has expanded their therapeutic applications beyond their original indications. The polyketide griseofulvin (**8**) which was isolated in 1939 from *Penicillium griseofulvum*, which was first marketed as an antimycotic as a treatment for dermatophytosis [Petersen et al., 2014]. Later, gained some interest as a tubulin polymerization inhibitor to also be able to use as an anticancer agent [Rønneet et al., 2009]. Other examples of antifungal substances are the ascomycete-derived echinocandins. Originally echinocandin B (**9**) was isolated from *Aspergillus spinulosporus*, formerly known as *Aspergillus nidulans* var. *echinulatus* [Benz et al., 1974]. Nowadays there are three different semi-synthetic derivatives on the market to treat invasive mycoses and severe forms of candidiasis. They are mostly cyclic lipodepsipeptides which are inhibiting the 1,3- β -D-glucan synthesis in fungal cell walls [Chen et al., 2011].

Furthermore, the investigation of fungal metabolites has led to significant findings in anticancer research. Illudins, a class of acylfulvene sesquiterpenoids, were first identified in the 1950s from various species of *Omphalotus*. These first found compounds, illudins M and S (**10**), are characterised by an unusual cyclopropane ring and have been extensively studied for their cytotoxicity against various tumor cell types [Kelner et al., 1990; Sandargo et al., 2019]. Despite their initial high toxicity against normal cells, which limited their direct use as anticancer agents, illudins have paved the way for the development of semi-synthetic analogs with improved therapeutic properties. One such derivative is irofulven (**11**), a semi-synthetic analog of illudin S, which exhibits a unique mechanism of action by being rapidly absorbed by tumor cells with high transcriptional activity [Tanasova and Sturla, 2012]. This disrupts DNA replication and induces tumor-specific apoptosis. Irofulven has undergone several phase II clinical trials, including for late-stage prostate cancer, highlighting its potential as an anticancer agent. Recent research has also produced new-generation illudin analogs with enhanced tumor specificity, such as chlorambucil and M-ferrocene conjugates [Schobert et al., 2008].

Beside the properties of fungal natural products as an antibiotic or anticancer agents, the fungal kingdom also produced other remarkable natural products which had a huge impact on different areas of medicine. The isolation of cyclosporine A (**12**) from *Tolypocladium inflatum* in the early 1970s marked a significant advancement in the field of immunopharmacology [Tedesco and Haragsim, 2012]. Initially discovered in 1971 during a search for new antifungal compounds, this cyclic peptide soon demonstrated powerful immunosuppressive capabilities. Research conducted in the 1980s demonstrated the potential of modulating T-cell function with minimal toxicity, paving the way for its development and approval as an immunosuppressive agent [Borel, 1976]. Cyclosporine A became the first drug to effectively prevent organ transplant rejection, revolutionizing transplantation procedures and showcasing the vast potential of fungal natural products in medical treatments. It continues to be a vital medication in transplant medicine, reflecting its long-term impact and success [Aly et al., 2011; World Health Organization, 2023].

Another class of drugs derived from fungal metabolites that has been highly successful is that of the statins. These have significantly impacted the management of cholesterol and cardiovascular health. The naturally occurring lovastatin (**13**), produced by *Aspergillus terreus*, was the first statin introduced to the market under the trade name Mevacor® in the late 1980s [Barrios-González and Miranda, 2009]. This pioneering cholesterol-lowering agent inhibits HMG-CoA reductase, a key enzyme in the cholesterol biosynthesis pathway. Following lovastatin's introduction, various semisynthetic or synthetic analogues, such as fluvastatin, pravastatin, atorvastatin, simvastatin, and rosuvastatin, have been developed and commercially released [Toth and Banach, 2019]. The sustained success and efficacy of statins has positioned them as one of the highest-revenue pharmaceuticals globally [Niego et al., 2023].

In addition to their broad application in human medicine, fungal secondary metabolites have been successfully utilized in veterinary medicine and agriculture for crop protection. Strobilurins represent a crucial class of agricultural fungicides. Initially isolated from a culture of *Strobilurus tenacellus* in the mid-1970s, strobilurins A (**14**) and B were discovered by Anke and colleagues [Anke et al., 1977]. These compounds, including natural congeners such as oudemansin A from *Mucidula mucida*, formerly included in *Oudemansiella*, feature a distinctive (E)- β -

methoxyacrylate group. By binding to cytochrome b, strobilurins inhibit mitochondrial respiration, leading to blocked ATP production. This disruption in the energy cycle prevents mycelial growth and spore germination within fungi. Their potent antifungal activity, combined with low toxicity to mammals, rendered them promising fungicide candidates for the application in agriculture [Feng et al., 2020]. This led to the development of synthetic analogues with improved fungicidal activity, such as azoxystrobin and kresoxim-methyl. Azoxystrobin, the first synthetic strobilurin fungicide, was introduced to the market in 1996. Subsequently, various strobilurin fungicides, have been developed and commercialized. The success of strobilurin fungicides in the late 1990s marked a significant advancement in agricultural chemistry. However, their single-site specific mechanism of action made them prone to resistance development shortly after their market introduction [Zhang et al., 2009]. Despite resistance issues, azoxystrobin and kresoxim-methyl remain widely used, often in mixture formulations to enhance their efficacy and durability. Research into strobilurins continues to reveal new derivatives, such as the 9-oxo strobilurin derivatives from *Favolaschia calocera*, discovered from Kenya [Chepkirui et al., 2016]. These ongoing discoveries underscore the potential of strobilurins as lead compounds for developing novel agricultural fungicides. The significant antifungal activity and low cytotoxicity of strobilurins towards mammals and plants, coupled with their feasibility for total synthesis, highlight their importance in the agrochemical industry [Aly et al., 2011].

Another notable example is emodepside (**15**), a semisynthetic derivative of the fungal cyclodepsipeptide PF1022A (**16**), isolated from *Rosellinia* species. This compound was discovered in the early 1990s and represents the first anthelmintically active member of the cyclooctadepsipeptides class [Sasaki et al., 1992]. PF1022A, derived from an endophytic fungus associated with the *Camellia japonica*, served as the lead compound for developing emodepside, which offers an enhanced spectrum of activity against parasitic nematodes. Emodepside is highly effective against a wide range of nematodes in various animal hosts, including those resistant to traditional anthelmintics like benzimidazoles, levamisole, or ivermectin. It is currently marketed under the trade name Profender[®], in combination with praziquantel, for treating gastrointestinal nematode and cestode infections in cats and dogs [Aly et al., 2011; Böhm et al., 2015].

Beside the discovery of illudins, another significant group of compounds produced by *Omphalotus* species are the omphalotins. These cyclic dodecapeptides, first isolated from the jack-o'-lantern mushroom *Omphalotus olearius* in the late 1990s, are highly selective nematocides [Sternner et al., 1997]. Omphalotins exhibit strong activity against root-knot nematodes like *Meloidogyne incognita* and are produced exclusively by species of the *Omphalotus* genus. The discovery of omphalotin A (**17**) marked the beginning of a series of investigations into these peptides. Subsequent research identified several derivatives with pronounced nematocidal properties, underscoring the potential of these natural products in agricultural applications especially offering promising avenue for nematode control [Mayer et al., 1999; Liermann et al., 2009].

In conclusion, the rich diversity of secondary metabolites produced by fungi continues to be a valuable resource with significant implications for drug discovery. Beyond that, the diverse applications of these compounds, ranging from antibiotics and immunosuppressant's to anthelmintics and fungicides, underscore the critical role of fungi in biomedicine and/or agriculture. Ongoing research and biotechnological innovations promise to unlock even more potential from these natural products, addressing current challenges in healthcare and environmental sustainability and various industrial applications.

Figure 1.1. Important natural products and derived drugs from fungi

Nematodes

Nematodes, a diverse and widely distributed group metazoans, inhabit a variety of environments including freshwater, marine and terrestrial biospheres. They exhibit varied lifestyles and are ranging from free-living to parasitic. Parasitic nematodes interact either directly or as a vector with hosts across a range of organisms, including plants, invertebrates and higher animals [Decraemer and Hunt, 2013]. Plant parasitic nematodes (PPNs) represent a significant proportion of nematodes, comprising for 15% of total described species. These PPNs are terrestrial with a widespread distribution, exhibiting obligate parasitic behaviour targeting below as well as above-ground plant tissues [Holterman et al., 2017]. They have a significant impact on plant health and the resulting yield decline combined with their long-term interaction poses significant challenges for global food security [De Waele and Elsen, 2007; Nicol et al., 2011]. With a diverse range of species and varying feeding mechanisms, each PPN impacts differently the plant. The life cycle of PPNs generally involves an egg stage followed by four juvenile stages that develop into adult females and males through a series of molts [Decraemer and Hunt, 2013]. The classification of PPNs is based on their feeding strategies and can be divided into three primary groups: ectoparasites, semi-endoparasites, and migratory and sedentary endoparasites [Decraemer and Hunt, 2013]. Ectoparasitic nematodes, such as *Xiphinema* and *Trichodorus*, are known to feed externally while remaining outside of root tissues in the soil. In contrast semi-endoparasites place only the anterior part in the root tissue, leaving the posterior part in the soil. Endoparasitic nematodes are divided into migratory, such as *Pratylenchus*, which penetrate plant roots, move and feed along plant tissue, and sedentary, including root-knot nematodes and cyst-forming nematodes [Perry and Moens, 2011; Decraemer and Hunt, 2013]. Root-knot nematodes (*Meloidogyne* spp.) and cyst-forming nematodes (e.g. *Globodera* and *Heterodera* spp.) particularly causing significant damage, as they exclusively target plant roots and rank among the most economically impacting PPNs [Jones et al., 2013].

In 1859, Schacht first reported *Heterodera schachtii* from sugar beets in Germany, marking the initial observation of a cyst nematode parasitizing a host plant. Subsequently, the genus *Heterodera* was established by Schmidt in 1871 to classify cyst-forming nematodes [Toumi et al.,

2017]. Among the *Heterodera* species, the cereal cyst nematodes (CCNs) are particularly significant. The Avenae group, which is one of seven taxonomic groups within the genus *Heterodera*, includes notable species such as *H. avenae*, *H. filipjevi*, and *H. latipons*, which are prevalent in most cereal-growing regions [Nicol et al., 2011]. The first CCN affecting cereals was reported by Kühn in 1874 in Germany and later identified as *H. avenae* [Kühn, 1874; Wollenweber, 1924]. CCN infestations are a major factor contributing to yield reduction with substantial economic impact in cereal production. These nematodes are especially damaging when combined with abiotic stresses, such as drought. The impact of CCNs is particularly severe in semi-arid regions where drought stress is common, leading to significant yield reductions [Nicol et al., 2011; Jones et al., 2013]. Effective management strategies are essential to reduce the economic losses caused by these nematodes in cereal crops.

Various approaches can be employed to minimize the impact of PPNs. The European Union (EU) and the majority of countries worldwide have prohibited the use of nematicides in agriculture. This ban is based on the toxicity of previous nematicide agents, such as methyl bromide, which have been shown to have adverse effects on soil microorganisms, and other organisms such as vertebrates, including humans [Nordbring-Hertz et al., 2011]. Environmentally friendly methods “for reduction of number of nematodes on fields” include implementing good agricultural practices e.g., breeding resistance crops, practicing crop rotation, and utilizing biological control methods [Dababat et al., 2015; Smiley et al., 2017; Toumi et al., 2017]. Biological control primarily focuses on regulating pest populations through the use of living organisms [Kwenti, 2017]. Among these, nematophagous fungi, a phylogenetically diverse group of fungi capable of killing nematodes, were among the first microorganisms recognized as parasites [Kühn, 1877]. These fungi play a crucial role in biological control strategies against PPNs, offering a sustainable approach to managing nematode populations and reducing their detrimental effects on crop yields.

Nematophagous fungi

Nematophagous fungi represent a unique group of microfungi known for their ability to capture, kill, and digest nematodes. These fungi are natural predators of nematodes and infect various

developmental stages (eggs, juveniles and adults) by utilizing specialized mycelial structures, such as traps and spores to ensnare nematode. Other structures like hyphal tips or appressoria are used to penetrate nematode eggs and cysts. Regardless of the infection method employed, the result is always the death of the nematodes [Nordbring-Hertz et al., 2011]. Nematophagous fungi exhibit extensive phylogenetic diversity, encompassing Ascomycota, Basidiomycota, Blastocladiomycota, and Zygomycota, as well as fungus-like organisms in the Oomycota [Lopez-Llorca et al., 2008]. The infection mechanisms of these fungi involve a sophisticated interplay of infection structures and biochemical processes. The infection process includes several stages. The process begins with the recognition stage, which is mediated by physical and enzymatic actions. At the initial recognition stage, cell-cell communication occurs, which subsequently initiates the production of adhesive proteins such as lectins, which have been demonstrated to accumulate and facilitate the recognition and adhesion to the nematode surface or eggshells [Tunlid and Ahrén, 2011; Li et al., 2015]. To overcome the additional physical barriers, present in nematode cuticles and eggshells, such as chitin, lipids and proteins, it is hypothesised that the fungus is producing exoenzymes, including chitinase, lipase and protease, in order to facilitate penetration of the cell wall and subsequent colonisation of the nematode [Bird and McClure, 1976; Morton et al., 2004]. Following the process of colonisation, the final stage is the digestion of the nematode. They are classified into three main categories based on their infection mechanisms: nematode-trapping, endoparasitic and egg- and cyst parasitic fungi [Li et al., 2015]. Nematode-trapping fungi are described from a variety of large taxonomic groups of fungi, including ascomycetes, basidiomycetes, and zygomycetes, and they are often present in soil environments [Nordbring-Hertz et al., 2011]. Baral et al. [2018] classify most ascomycetous nematode-trapping fungi within *Arthrobotrys sensu lato*, a monophyletic group in the Orbiliaceae family [Baral et al., 2018]. These fungi form a variety of trapping structures, which may or may not contain an adhesive layer. These structures often feature branches, knobs, constricting rings, and networks. The adhesive layer consists of polymers that bind to the nematode surface [Tunlid and Ahrén, 2011]. Constricting rings capture nematodes by mechanical swelling. Trap formation in nematode-trapping fungi is induced by nematode presence and presented or secreted molecules, like nemin and ascarosides [Nordbring-Hertz, 2004; Li et al., 2015].

Endoparasitic fungi employ their spores or conidia to parasitize nematodes, utilizing various mechanisms such as adhering to the host cuticle, being ingested by the nematode, or being injected into the nematode's body cavity [Lopez-Llorca et al., 2006]. Notable examples within the Ascomycota include *Drechmeria coniospora* (Clavicipitaceae, Hypocreales), which generates adhesive knobs, thereby enabling attachment to the nematode cuticle and the initiation of infections [Dijksterhuis et al., 1990]. Another example is the ingestion of conidia of the species *Harposporium*, which germinate and colonise the host starting from the digestive system [Wang et al., 2007].

Egg-parasitic fungi employ a range of specialized structures, including appressoria and hyphal penetration, to facilitate colonization of the host [Morgan-Jones et al., 1984; Lopez-Llorca et al., 2002]. In the initial stages of infection, the hyphae wind themselves around or adhere tightly to the eggshell. Subsequently, the host is penetrated and colonised, a process that may encompass mechanical, biochemical and enzymatic processes [Lopez-Llorca et al., 2008; Li et al., 2015]. Notable species include *Pochonia chlamydosporia*, *Metapochonia rubescens*, *Metarhizium* spp., *Lecanicillium lecanii*, and *Purpureocillium lilacinum*.

Interest in nematophagous fungi research is motivated by their potential use as biological control agents to combat plant-parasitic nematodes. In particular, egg- and cyst-parasitic fungi have shown significant promise as biocontrol agents. Kerry and Crump [1998] found that the natural antagonistic potential against nematode *Heterodera avenae*, involving the egg-parasitic fungi *Pochonia chlamydosporia* and *Nematophthora gynophila*, was diminished following formalin soil treatments [Kerry and Crump, 1998]. This reduction in fungal density led to a significant increase in cyst nematode populations. Once formalin treatments were discontinued, the densities of these fungi recovered, and *H. avenae* populations declined to pre-treatment levels. Soils that exhibit nematode-suppressive properties typically harbor a variety of nematode-antagonistic organisms, which collectively lower PPN population densities [Kerry, 1988; Westphal, 2005]. Exploring the microbial communities in these suppressive soils can yield microorganisms with high biocontrol potential against PPNs [Kerry et al., 1982; Saxena, 2018].

The exploration of nematophagous fungi extends beyond their ecological impact, as these organisms are also known as a source of interesting natural products with potential therapeutic or agricultural applications.

Natural products from nematophagous fungi

Nematophagous fungi produce a range of metabolites with diverse biological activities, including nematicidal properties, which have garnered significant interest for their potential use as environmentally friendly alternatives to chemical nematicides [Degenkolb and Vilcinskis, 2016].

The pioneering studies by Stadler and colleagues in the early 1990s demonstrated the role of nematophagous fungi as producers of several interesting metabolites. Nematode-trapping fungi, particularly *Arthrobotrys* spp., are known to produce several natural products, primarily of the oligosporon type. These include oligosporon (**18**), 4',5'-dihydro-oligosporon, flagranones A and B, and arthrobotrisins B and C. These compounds exhibited weak to moderate antimicrobial activity against gram-positive organisms such as *Bacillus* spp., *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Streptomyces aureofaciens*. In addition to its antimicrobial properties, oligosporon demonstrated moderate cytotoxicity against the HL 60 cell line. Furthermore, oligosporon and 4',5'-dihydro-oligosporon also exhibited weak nematicidal effects on the larvae of the nematode *Haemonchus contortus*, with LD₅₀ values of 25 µg/mL and 50-100 µg/mL, respectively [Stadler et al., 1993b; Anderson et al., 1995, 1999; Wei et al., 2011]. Arthrosporols A, B, and C, analogous molecules produced by *Arthrobotrys oligospora*, have been shown to regulate fungal morphology and the formation of nematode-trapping structures. In addition, arthrosporol C (**19**) inhibits the formation of conidiophores and conidial germination [Zhang et al., 2012]. Paganin A (**20**) and blumenol A are produced by *Dactylellina entomopaga* and function as a nematode attractant, guiding nematodes towards the fungal traps, thus facilitating their capture. Additionally, paganin A is increasing the formation of adhesive knobs [Wu et al., 2013]. A widespread metabolite across the fungal kingdom is lineoleic acid (**21**), which was isolated Stadler et al. [1993a] from *A. conoides* and it shows moderate activity against the nematode *Caenorhabditis elegans* [Stadler et al., 1993a].

Another well-studied nematophagous fungus is the egg-parasitic *Pochonia chlamydosporia*, known for producing a variety of natural products. This fungus synthesizes numerous polyketides, particularly but not limited to resorcylic acid lactones, including pochonins (pochonin A, **22**), monordens, and monocillins (monocillin II, **23**). As reported by Hellwig et al. [2003], many of these metabolites demonstrated antiviral activity against herpes simplex virus 1 and anti-parasitic effects against the protozoan cause of coccidiosis in chicken, *Eimeria tenella*, in addition to their cytotoxic properties [Hellwig et al., 2003]. Monorden (**24**), in particular, exhibits a broad spectrum of antifungal activities and has been subject of investigation for its potential application as an anticancer agent [Ayer et al., 1980; Hellwig et al., 2003]. In addition to resorcylic acid lactones, *Pochonia chlamydosporia* produces other significant metabolites, including aurovertins (including aurovertin D, E, F, and I) and phomalactone. Aurovertin D (**25**) shows moderate toxicity towards the root-knot nematode *Meloidogyne incognita* by disrupting its energy metabolism through the inhibition of mitochondrial ATP synthase [Wang et al., 2015]. Furthermore, phomalactone (**26**) has also been shown to have a moderate, delayed lethal effect on the second-stage juveniles of *Meloidogyne incognita* [Khambay et al., 2000].

The genus *Paecilomyces* has also been the subject of considerable scientific study regarding the produced metabolites. This is exemplified by strains of *Paecilomyces variotii*, which were isolated from different sources, including eggs of soybean cyst nematode *Heterodera glycines*. They are known to produce antifungal sphingofungins E (**27**) and F, semi-viriditoxin (**28**) and the dimer the mycotoxin viriditoxin (**29**) [Ayer et al., 1991; Horn et al., 1992; Houbraken et al., 2006].

Recent studies of different fungal species isolated from the cereal cyst nematode *Heterodera filipjevi* by Ashrafi and collaborators have shown again the potential of nematophagous fungi to produce a broad spectrum of active metabolites [Ashrafi et al., 2017; Helaly et al., 2018; Moussa et al., 2020]. Cereal cyst associated fungi *Ijuhya vitellina* produces the cytotoxic chaetoglobosins A (**30**) and B, including their 19-*O*-acetyl derivatives. In addition this fungus has been reported to produce moderately nematocidal compounds leucinostatins Q (**31**), P and U against the free-living nematode *C. elegans* [Ashrafi et al., 2017; Moussa et al., 2020]. Another cereal cyst-associated fungi with broad spectrum of produced metabolites is *Polydomus karssenii*, which produces the

novel arthrichitins B and C as well as the ophiotine (**32**). The later compound showed weak nematicidal activity against the host nematode *H. filipjevi* [Helaly et al., 2018; Ashrafi et al., 2023].

Natural products derived from fungi represent promising source for novel bioactive compounds. The majority fungal species is poorly studied or not explored yet, with nematophagous fungi representing a particularly promising yet under-investigated group. They have developed specialised mechanisms for parasitising nematodes. Consequently they represent an underexplored reservoir of bioactive compounds against plant parasitic nematodes as well as other important targets for pharmaceutical and biotechnological research [Degenkolb and Vilcinskas, 2016].

Figure 1.2. Metabolites produced by nematophagous fungi

Aim and outline of the Thesis

The introduction of the thesis aims to highlight the historical importance and unexploited potential of fungi, especially nematophagous fungi, in discovering new natural products to address current global challenges. The thesis is centered on the isolation of novel natural products, with a particular focus on their biological characterisation from nematophagous fungi and related species from a variety of geographical origins. The hypothesis of the study is that due to the unique predatory lifestyle and broad biochemical arsenal of these fungi, they may produce compounds with novel modes of action against several organisms of interest.

Using a combination of microbiological and chemical analytical techniques, we systematically screened various fungal strains for their capabilities in the synthesis of biologically active secondary metabolites. In the following sections, I detail the methodology employed in the screening, isolation, structure elucidation, and biological characterisation of these compounds. We present our findings on their antimicrobial efficacy and discuss the implications of our results for the broader field of natural product research. Additionally, we evaluate the potential use of these fungi as a biocontrol strategy.

Our investigation reveals the presence of several previously unidentified compounds from the genus *Polyphilus* (publication I-II), the species *Laburnicola nematophila* (publication III-V), *Polydomus karssenii* (VI) and unpublished data from *Pochonia chlamydosporia* beside the strains mentioned before. These findings contribute to the expanding repertoire of natural products with therapeutic potential and underscore the importance of ecological interactions in uncovering new leads for drug development.

2. Methodology

Fungal material

In this thesis, the fungal strains under investigation were provided by Samad Ashrafi from the Julius Kühn Institute (JKI - Federal Research Centre for Cultivated Plants). Particular attention was directed towards fungi isolated from the eggs of the cereal cyst nematode, *Heterodera filipjevi*, which were collected in a recent survey of agricultural fields in Turkey. Additional comparative

analyses were conducted with related strains of different origins to assess their similarities and possible differences to those parasitizing nematode eggs. The isolation procedure, morphological description, and multigene phylogeny are referenced in Table X. All strains were maintained on YM 6.3 agar (10 g L⁻¹ malt extract, 4 g L⁻¹ D-glucose, 4 g L⁻¹ yeast extract, 20 g L⁻¹ agar, pH 6.3) at 23°C in the dark.

Table 2.1. List of examined isolates

Order	Genus	Species	Strain ID	Host	Isolation source	Reference		
Helotiales	Polyphilus	sieberi	Ref052	<i>Asclepias syriaca</i>	roots	[Ashrafi et al., 2018]		
			TT3A	<i>Hydnobolytes cf. sp.</i>	ascoma			
			P1582	<i>Microthlaspi erraticum</i>	roots			
			M03	<i>Populus deltoides x P. nigra</i>	roots			
				17A				
				17A-5	<i>Heterodera filipjevi</i>		cyst/egg	
				17C				
				frankenii	Ref050		<i>Juniperus communis</i>	roots
			V16	<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>	roots			
Hypocreales	Pochonia	chlamydosporia	66T	<i>H. filipjevi</i>	cyst/egg	unpublished		
Pleosporales	Laburnicola	nematophila	20K3			[Knapp et al., 2022]		
			20K1	<i>H. filipjevi</i>	cyst/egg			
			20AD					
Pleosporales	Polydomus	karssenii	P1579			[Glynou et al., 2016]		
			P6108	<i>M. perfoliatum</i>	roots			
			P2870					
			P2789					
			YE1	<i>H. filipjevi</i>	cyst/egg		[Ashrafi et al., 2023]	
			5BD					

HPLC profiling of secondary metabolites

To investigate the secondary metabolite profiles of the fungal strains, a diverse set of media was chosen to identify optimal growth conditions and a diversity of secondary metabolites. YM 6.3 (10 g L⁻¹ malt extract, 4 g L⁻¹ D-glucose, 4 g L⁻¹ yeast extract, pH 6.3), Q6/2 (10 g L⁻¹ glycerol, 5 g L⁻¹ cotton seed flour, 2.5 g L⁻¹ D-glucose, pH 7.2), and ZM/2 (5 g L⁻¹ molasses, 5 g L⁻¹ oat flour, 4 g L⁻¹ mannitol, 4 g L⁻¹ sucrose, 1.5 g L⁻¹ CaCO₃, 1.5 g L⁻¹ D-glucose, 0.5 g L⁻¹ lactalbumin enzymatic hydrolysate, 0.5 g L⁻¹ (NH₄)₂SO₄, pH 7.2) were chosen as submerged media. BRFT and WOFT (1 g L⁻¹ yeast extract, 0.5 g L⁻¹ K₂HPO₄, 0.5 g L⁻¹ sodium tartrate; 100 mL solution was added to 28 g brown rice/whole oats before autoclaving) were chosen as solid fermentation media.

Screening cultivation

For each liquid medium, five 25 mm² segments of a well-grown culture on YM 6.3 media were used to inoculate 200 mL of the tested media in a 500 mL Erlenmeyer flask. The cultures were incubated at 23°C on a rotary shaker at 140 rpm in the dark. To investigate the impact of different cultivation times, the fermentation was terminated 2 and 5 days after glucose consumption. Glucose levels were measured daily using Medi-Test Glucose strips (Machery-Nagel®, Düren, Germany). Six 500 mL Erlenmeyer flasks were used for each of the solid media, which were harvested in duplicates after 2, 3, and 4 weeks.

Extraction of secondary metabolites

The culture broth and the mycelia were separated from submerged cultures using vacuum filtration with a Büchner funnel lined with a filter disk. The pH was measured with a pH meter, and the supernatant was extracted three times with an equal volume of fresh ethyl acetate in a separatory funnel. The combined organic phase was dried with anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and then evaporated under vacuum with a rotary evaporator at 40°C. The dried crude extract of the supernatant was transferred with acetone and methanol to a 4 mL brown glass vial and dried under N₂ flow at 37°C. The weight of the wet biomass was determined, then covered with acetone and extracted in an ultrasonic bath at 40°C for 30 minutes. The acetone was filtered with filter paper, and the mycelium was covered with fresh acetone and the extraction was repeated

two more times. The combined acetone extracts were evaporated under vacuum until the aqueous phase remained, which was treated as described for the supernatant.

The solid-state fermentation was terminated by adding acetone, and the subsequent steps followed the mycelia extraction procedure used for liquid cultures. To remove the high percentage of fatty acids, the crude extract from the previous step was dissolved in 5 mL of methanol and extracted twice with 45 mL of fresh heptane. Both fractions were dried and retained for further analysis.

Analytical high-performance liquid chromatography for dereplication and identification of novel secondary metabolites

The crude extracts obtained from the screening cultures were analyzed by high-performance liquid chromatography-diode array detection coupled to a mass spectrometer (HPLC-DAD/MS). The dried samples were quantified and diluted to a concentration of 4.5 mg/mL in methanol or acetone, and 2 μ L were subjected to the HPLC system (UltiMate[®] 3000 Series uHPLC, Thermo Fisher Scientific[®], Waltman, MA, USA) coupled to an electrospray ionization (ESI) ion trap mass spectrometer (amaZon speed[®] by Bruker), utilizing an Acquity-UPLC[®] BEH C18 Column (2.1 x 50 mm, 1.7 μ m; Waters, Milford, CT, USA). The following parameters were used: the mobile phase consisted of solvent A (deionized water + 0.1% formic acid (FA)) and solvent B (acetonitrile (ACN) + 0.1% FA), following the gradient of 5% B for 0.5 min, increasing to 100% B in 19.5 min, maintaining 100% B for an additional 5 minutes; flow rate was 0.6 mL/min; DAD detection ranged from 190–600 nm.

To determine the structural formulae of produced metabolites for the most promising extracts, the samples were measured at a concentration of 1 mg/mL using HPLC-high resolution MS (HPLC-HRMS). The spectra were recorded with a combination of an Agilent 1200 Infinity Series HPLC (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) and a maXis[®] ESI time-of-flight mass spectrometer (ESI-TOF-MS, Bruker) with the same parameters as mentioned above, with an additional scan range of 100–2500 m/z, a rate of 2 Hz, a capillary voltage of 4500 V, and a dry temperature of 200°C. The spectra were evaluated using Bruker DataAnalysis software (version 6.1).

The gathered information about each signal, including retention time, DAD spectra, and molecular formula, which could be deduced from the fragmentation pattern of the HRMS spectra. This data was used to compare the secondary metabolites with commercially available databases such as the Dictionary of Natural Products and Sci-Finder, as well as publicly accessible databases like the Natural Product Atlas for dereplication.

Screening for bioactive natural products

There are several approaches to screen for bioactive natural products, such as phenotypic screening with agar-diffusion assays, serial dilution assays, or activity-guided fractionation against different indicator strains. Chemical screenings involve isolating the full range of produced natural products and subsequently testing them in various assays to determine their activity. In this thesis, phenotypic screening was conducted with the crude extracts of the liquid cultures, and chemical screening was performed for the purified metabolites from larger scale fermentations.

For the phenotypic screening of the obtained crude extracts, a serial dilution assay was performed in a 96-well plate. The indicator strains used were Gram-positive *Bacillus subtilis* (DSM 10), Gram-negative *Escherichia coli* (DSM 1116), the yeast *Candida albicans* (DSM 1665), and the filamentous fungi *Mucor hiemalis* (DSM 2656). To determine the minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC), the crude extracts were dissolved in methanol or DMSO (1:10) to a concentration of 4.5 mg/mL. Cell suspensions of *E. coli*, *C. albicans*, and *M. hiemalis* were prepared from stocks and adjusted to 0.01 OD at 600 nm in Mueller–Hinton Broth medium for *E. coli*, and to 0.1 OD at 600 nm for *C. albicans*. *B. subtilis* was used from an overnight culture at 30°C and 200 rpm in MHB and adjusted to 0.01 OD at 600 nm for the assay.

A total of 150 µL of the microorganism suspensions were dispensed into each well of a 96-well microtiter plate. The initial row (A) received 130 µL of the suspension combined with 20 µL of the tested extract. The test ranged from MIC values of 300 – 2.35 µg/mL. Methanol served as a solvent control, while nystatin and ciprofloxacin, starting at 66.6 µg/mL, were used as positive controls for fungi and bacteria, respectively. The plates were incubated overnight at 600 rpm on

a microplate shaker at 30°C, except for *E. coli*, which was incubated at 37°C. The MIC was determined after 24 hours, or in the case of *M. hiemalis*, after 48 hours.

Larger scale cultivation and extraction

The strains to be cultivated in larger volumes were selected based on various parameters such as bioactivity in initial screening, presence of assumed novel metabolites, yield, and complexity of the crude extract. To investigate both minor and major metabolites in strains of interest, optimal growth conditions, including cultivation time and media, were determined, and the cultivation volume was increased. Liquid cultivation was performed with 400 mL of medium in twelve 1 L Erlenmeyer flasks, resulting in a total volume of 4.8 L. For a homogeneous cultivation process, a seed culture was used to inoculate each flask. The seed culture was prepared in Q6/2 medium following the protocol in the media screening section. After reaching the desired concentration of biomass without consuming the free glucose in the culture broth, the seed culture was homogenized using an Ultra-Turrax (T25 easy clean digital, IKA) equipped with an S25 N-25F dispersing tool at 10,000 rpm for 10 seconds. A volume of 0.5% (2 mL) for each flask was used for inoculation.

After the free glucose was consumed, three flasks were selected for small-scale extraction to provide information about the production of the desired metabolites. Under sterile conditions, 2 mL of culture broth was removed and placed in a 15 mL conical reaction tube, then covered with an equal volume of ethyl acetate. The mixture was shaken for 30 seconds and then placed in an ultrasonic bath for an additional 15 minutes. To separate the aqueous from the organic phase, the tube was centrifuged for 5 minutes at 4000 rpm. Subsequently, 1.8 mL of ethyl acetate was removed from the top layer, transferred to a 4 mL vial, and dried under nitrogen flow. The dried crude extract was dissolved in 100 µL of methanol and acetone (1:1), and 2 µL was subjected to HPLC-ESIMS as mentioned above.

Purification of natural products

The crude extracts were analyzed using HPLC–DAD/MS, as detailed earlier, to identify the general composition of each extract. This analysis also aimed to detect significant concentrations of

hydrophobic molecules, such as fatty acids and steroids, which could hinder further isolation procedures and decrease the solubility of extracts in solvents used for reversed-phase (RP) HPLC. When high levels of these hydrophobic compounds were detected, the initial step in their isolation involved solubilizing the extract in dichloromethane (DCM), n-heptane, or a mixture thereof. This solution was then applied to a normal phase (NP) middle-pressure liquid chromatography (NP-MPLC) system using a Grace Reveleris® X2 Flash system equipped with Büchi FlashPure ID Silica cartridges in different sizes, depending on the overall extract amount. The compounds with higher hydrophobicity were eluted first, while the more hydrophilic constituents were removed using a mobile phase of higher polarity. The eluates were collected separately, dried under reduced pressure at 40°C in a rotary evaporator, and analyzed by HPLC-DAD/MS. This procedure was performed with all mycelial and solid-state fermentation extracts.

Further purification steps were performed using different preparative RP-HPLC devices, such as the PLC 2050 and PLC 2250 (Gilson, Middleton, WI, USA), or the FlashPrep 850C (Büchi Labortechnik AG, Flawil, Switzerland), with various C18 columns as the stationary phase (e.g., Nucleodur C18ec, 250x40 mm, 10 µm; Machery-Nagel, Düren, Germany, or Gemini C18, 250x50 mm, 10 µm; Phenomenex, Torrance, CA, USA). The mobile phase consisted of ultrapure water and acetonitrile (ACN), both supplemented with 0.1% formic acid. Further purification was achieved through additional RP-HPLC steps employing different gradients and columns with varying materials or finer particle sizes (e.g., X-Bridge C18, 250x19 mm, 5 µm; Waters, Millford, MA, USA), using the same HPLC systems. Amounts smaller than 5 mg were purified using an Agilent Technologies 1200 Infinity Series semi-preparative system.

Metabolite characterisation

Isolated compounds were subjected to HPLC-HRMS to assess purity and derive molecular formulae, with concentrations ranging from 0.1 to 1 mg/mL in appropriate solvents. To elucidate structural configurations, compounds of sufficient purity were dissolved in different deuterated solvents, including acetone-d₆, dimethylsulfoxide-d₆ (DMSO-d₆), and chloroform-d (CDCl₃-d), and subsequently transferred into nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy tubes. Quantities exceeding 2 mg were dissolved in 600 µL of solvent and placed in standard 5 mm NMR

tubes. For lesser quantities, a reduced volume of 220 μ L of solvent and 3 mm NMR tubes was used. NMR spectral analysis was conducted using an Avance III 700 spectrometer (equipped with a 5 mm TCI cryoprobe, operating at ^1H : 700 MHz and ^{13}C : 175 MHz) and an Avance III 500 spectrometer (^1H : 500 MHz, ^{13}C : 125 MHz; both instruments manufactured by Bruker). Different measurements were performed, including one-dimensional ^1H and ^{13}C NMR, as well as two-dimensional techniques such as $^1\text{H}/^1\text{H}$ correlation spectroscopy (COSY), $^1\text{H}/^{13}\text{C}$ nuclear single quantum correlation (HSQC), and $^1\text{H}/^{13}\text{C}$ heteronuclear multiple bond correlation (HMBC) for structural determination. Where appropriate, $^1\text{H}/^1\text{H}$ rotational nuclear Overhauser effect spectroscopy (ROESY) was applied for the assignment of relative stereochemistry.

The determination of absolute stereochemistry was facilitated by the chiral derivatisation of secondary alcohols via Mosher's method, in conjunction with analysis of specific spectroscopic data. To determine configurations of amino acids, the advanced Marfey's method was used. Further, the assignment of absolute stereochemistry was supported through the measurement of optical rotation using an MCP 150 polarimeter (Anton Paar, Graz, Austria) and the acquisition of electronic circular dichroism (ECD) spectra with a J-815 spectropolarimeter (Jasco, Pfungstadt, Germany). Comparative analysis with previously documented reference data facilitated the assignment of stereochemical configurations. Ultraviolet-visible (UV/VIS) spectra were obtained with a UV-2450 spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan).

Biological activity assay of pure compounds

Purified metabolites in sufficient quantities were tested in a wide array of biological assays. The screening included tests for antimicrobial, antifungal, and nematicide effects, and in specific cases, antiviral assays (publication III) or effects on biofilm formation of *Staphylococcus aureus* (publication II). Details concerning the activity of isolated and described compounds are provided in publications I-V.

Antimicrobial assay

The antimicrobial efficacy of each isolated metabolite was assessed by Wera Collisi (MWIS, Helmholtz Centre for Infection Research (HZI)) by determining their minimum inhibitory

concentrations (MICs) against a panel of five fungal species (*Candida albicans*, *Mucor hiemalis*, *Rhodotorula glutinis*, *Schizosaccharomyces pombe*, and *Wickerhamomyces anomalus*), as well as several Gram-positive (*Bacillus subtilis*, *Mycobacterium smegmatis*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*) and Gram-negative bacteria (*Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Chromobacterium violaceum*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*). The methodology employed followed standard protocols (publication II).

Bacterial suspensions, except for *M. smegmatis*, were prepared in Mueller–Hinton Broth (Carl Roth GmbH, Karlsruhe, Germany) and adjusted to an optical density (OD) of 0.01 at 600 nm. *M. smegmatis* was cultured in Middlebrook 7H9 Broth Base supplemented with Middlebrook ADC Growth Supplement (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) and adjusted to an OD of 0.1 at 548 nm. The fungal strains were cultivated in MYC medium and adjusted to a similar OD as *M. smegmatis*. Methanol served as the negative control, while various positive controls were utilized depending on the organism tested: Nystatin (1 mg/mL) for fungi, Oxytetracycline for *B. subtilis*, and specific antibiotics such as Ciprofloxacin for *Acinetobacter baumannii*, Kanamycin for *M. smegmatis*, and Gentamicin for *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. This setup facilitated a serial dilution of the test compounds across the plate, ranging from 66.7 µg/mL to 0.52 µg/mL. The plates were then incubated overnight at 800 rpm on a microplate shaker. All organisms were cultured at 30°C, except for *M. smegmatis*, *E. coli*, and *P. aeruginosa*, which were cultured at 37°C. The MIC was determined as the lowest concentration at which the compounds prevented visible growth of the organisms.

Cytotoxic assay

The cytotoxic effects of the isolated metabolites were assessed by Wera Collisi (MWIS, HZI) on two mammalian cell lines: human endocervical adenocarcinoma KB 3.1 and mouse fibroblasts L929. This evaluation was performed in 96-well plates. The compounds were prepared in the same solvents mentioned in the antimicrobial section, utilizing epothilone B as the positive control. The cell lines were incubated with these compounds, which were serially diluted to achieve final concentrations ranging from 37 to 0.6 µg/mL, at 37°C in an atmosphere containing

10% CO₂. The medium used was Gibco™ Dulbecco's Modified Eagle's Medium (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) enriched with 10% fetal bovine serum (Thermo Fisher Scientific).

After a five-day incubation period, cell viability was determined by staining with 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT, Sigma-Aldrich, Deisenhofen, Germany). This staining technique relies on the conversion of MTT to purple formazan by metabolically active cells, with the resultant intensity serving as a measure of cell viability compared to untreated cells (considered 100% viable). A microplate reader, set to 595 nm, facilitated the quantification of cell viability, enabling the determination of the half-maximum inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) values for each compound.

For cytotoxic compounds, the assay was extended to five additional cell lines: breast adenocarcinoma MCF-7, lung carcinoma A549, ovary adenocarcinoma SK-OV-3, prostate adenocarcinoma PC-3, and epidermoid carcinoma A431, following the same procedure.

Nematicidal assay

Caenorhabditis elegans were cultured on slightly modified nematode growth media (NGM) (3 g/L NaCl, 2.5 g/L soy peptone, 20 g/L agar, supplemented post-autoclaving at 55°C with: 1 mL cholesterol (5 mg/mL in ethanol), 1 mL 1 M CaCl₂, 1 mL 1 M MgSO₄, and 25 mL 1 M KPO₄) [Brenner, 1974], with an *E. coli* lawn as a food source. Cultures were maintained by transferring segments of cultured nematodes to fresh plates to sustain viability.

To ensure a synchronized population and increase reproducibility, a time with high egg density (~120 hours post inoculation) was chosen for bleaching. The NGM plates were washed three times with 4 mL of 0.9% NaCl solution and transferred to a 15 mL conical reaction tube. The suspension was centrifuged at 1100 g for 2 minutes, and the supernatant was discarded. This process was repeated until a clear nematode suspension was achieved. For bleaching, 3 mL of nematode suspension was mixed with 3 mL of bleaching solution (1 mL sodium hypochlorite solution, 1 mL 5 M NaOH, 6.25 mL ultra-pure H₂O) and monitored under a stereomicroscope until the disappearance of hatched nematodes. The suspension was then neutralized with 0.9% NaCl solution, washed as previously described, and the volume adjusted to 7 mL. This prepared

suspension was incubated at 23°C on a rotary shaker at 80 rpm for egg hatching. After 18 hours, hatched nematodes were transferred to fresh NGM plates with an *E. coli* lawn.

The population of *C. elegans*, consisting mostly of J4 and adult nematodes, was washed from the plate as described above, and their concentration adjusted to 1 nematode per μL with 0.9% NaCl solution. Test compounds, dissolved in methanol, were added to a 48-well plate and dried under a nitrogen stream. A total of 300 μL of nematode suspension was added to each well, with the final test concentrations being 100, 50, and 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, each in triplicate. Per plate, a total of 4 compounds in three concentrations were tested. The remaining wells were used for methanol as a negative control and ivermectin at a concentration of 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ as a positive control. After 15 minutes, immediate effects on *C. elegans* were checked, and the mortality rate was determined to see the influence of incubation time. The 48-well plates were sealed with parafilm and agitated for 18 hours at room temperature at 100 rpm. Post-incubation, mortality was assessed in triplicate by removing 3 x 30 μL from each well and counting both live and dead nematodes under a stereomicroscope; nematodes not moving and in an erect position were considered dead. Mortality was corrected with the Schneider-Orelli equation using the following equation to account for variable negative control [Ntalli et al., 2010]. A compound was deemed to have significant nematicidal activity if it achieved a lethal dose with at least 50% mortality at 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$.

3. Results and discussion

The thesis describes the cultivation, isolation, structure elucidation and biological assessment of secondary metabolites produced by fungal strains belonging to three different orders: Helotiales, Hypocreales and Pleosporales. By focusing on fungi from less-studied ecological niches and the application of diverse cultivation and purification techniques resulted in the isolation of 29 metabolites. These were identified through the comprehensive analysis of 1D and 2D nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy and high-resolution electrospray ionisation mass spectrometry (HRESIMS) data. Of these, 13 were identified as known metabolites, while the remaining 16 were previously undescribed. A variety of different test organisms were used for

their biological assessment, provided that the samples were isolated in sufficient quantities. These findings are detailed in publications I–V.

The publications I–II focuses on the genus *Polyphilus* (Hyaloscyphaceae, Helotiales) and examines two endophytic fungi, namely *P. frankenii* (V16 = DSM 106521) and *P. sieberi* (Ref052 = DSM 106515), which were isolated from the roots of *Pinus sylvestris* and *Asclepias syriaca*, respectively. Furthermore, two isolates of *P. sieberi* (17A = DSM 106517 and 17C = JKI 73000), which were obtained from infected eggs of the CCN *Heterodera filipjevi* [Ashrafi et al., 2018]. It should be noted that the metabolites isolated and identified from these species are not exclusive to specific strains; however, their production levels vary among isolates.

The research on *Polyphilus* sp. describes the isolation and characterisation of four previously undescribed naphtho- α -pyranone derivatives: the monomers semitalaroderxine C (**33**) and ventiloquinone P (**34**) beside two dimers named talaroderxine C (**35**) and D (**36**). Their absolute configurations were determined using a combination of ECD calculations and Mosher's method. Furthermore, the study identifies two new chlorinated cyclotetrapeptides, omnipolyphilins A (**37**) and B (**38**), whose absolute configuration were resolved via Marfey's method, ROESY correlations and TDDFT-ECD calculations. In addition to these novel compounds, several known metabolites were isolated, including outovirin A – C (**39 – 41**), (3S,6S)-3,6-dibenzylpiperazine-2,5-dione (**42**) and trichoderamide C (**43**), peniciadametizine B (**44**), ophiocordylongiiside A (**45**), lumichrome (**46**), fusidic acid (**47**), and 3-ketofusidic acid (**48**).

Talaroderxine C and D exhibited potent antibacterial activity, particularly against *B. subtilis* with MIC values of 0.52 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ and 2.1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, respectively, and *S. aureus* MIC values of 66.6 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ and 8.3 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, respectively. Inspired by the study of Helaly et al. [2019] on the structurally related pigmentosins A and B, further investigations of the effect on biofilm formation by *S. aureus* were conducted [Helaly et al., 2019]. The compounds showed significant biofilm inhibition, with up to 70% inhibition at concentration of 3.9 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ and 0.25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, respectively. Additionally, talaroderxine C and D exhibited cytotoxic effects on various mammalian cell lines, with IC_{50} values in the low micromolar to nanomolar range, particularly effective on MCF-7 and A431 with IC_{50} values between 0.068 and 2.38 μM .

The novel omnipolyphilin A, showed no significant activity in the bioassays performed. Among the tested known metabolites, only fusidic acid demonstrated significant effect on *B. subtilis* (MIC = 1.04 µg/mL) and *S. aureus* (MIC = 8.3 µg/mL), whereas it exhibited weak effect on *Mycobacterium smegmatis*. Ophiocordylongiiside A was the only nematicidal compound identified, showing significant lethal effects on *C. elegans* with a mortality rate of 69% at 100 µg/mL. Metabolites (**33**, **38 – 42**, **44**, **46**, **48**) were not isolated in sufficient amounts and were therefore not biologically characterised.

The genus *Polyphilus* has been identified as a prolific producer of a diverse range of metabolites. Among these, the 6-6' bisnaphthopyrones are notable for their presence across various fungal sources and their wide range of biological activities. Noteworthy metabolites with 6-6'-bisnaphthopyrone core-structure produced by *Penicillium dextrii* include talarodexine A and B, which exhibit antibacterial effects against *Bacillus subtilis* and act as inhibitors of botulinum neurotoxin serotype A [Suzuki et al., 1992; Cardellina et al., 2012]. Another significant compound from the group is viriditoxin, originally described in 1973 as a mycotoxin from *Aspergillus viridinutans*. Viriditoxin functions as an FtsZ polymerization inhibitor, demonstrating activity against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative pathogens of clinical importance, alongside exhibiting cytotoxic effects in mice [Lillehoj and Milburn, 1973; Wang et al., 2003]. Additionally, the gliovirin-like compound outovirin C has been characterised for its antifungal properties [Kajula et al., 2016]. Thiodiketopiperazine compounds, which feature a distinctive alpha-beta sulfide bridge between two amino acid residues, are known for their effectiveness against the cause of African trypanosomiasis *Trypanosoma brucei* and potential antitumor and anti-inflammatory properties [Rether et al., 2007; Iwatsuki et al., 2010].

Figure 3.1. Metabolites isolated from *Polyphilus* spp.

The investigation of three fungal strains of nematode-associated fungi from the recently introduced nematode species *Laburnicola nematophila* by Knapp et al. [2022] led to the identification and characterisation of 13 metabolites, including 10 novel compounds, as detailed in publications III to V [Knapp et al., 2022]. The studies successfully isolated six novel linear

peptides, named Laburnicotides A–F (**49** – **54**), with their stereochemistry determined using advanced Marfey's method combined with 1D and 2D NMR spectroscopy. Additionally, a rare penillic acid derivative, laburnicolamine (**55**), was characterised using NMR spectroscopy, and its absolute configuration was resolved using TDDFT-ECD calculations. Further isolation efforts led to the purification of three dactylfungins: YM-202204 (**56**), dactylfungin D (**57**), and the previously unknown dactylfungin C (**58**). These compounds exhibited significant antifungal activity, particularly against *Aspergillus fumigatus* and azole-resistant strains. Detailed evaluations revealed that dactylfungin D (S39163/F-I, 2) demonstrated high potency against *A. fumigatus* (MIC = 0.52 µg/mL) and its azole-resistant strains (MIC = 0.52 µg/mL), along with moderate activity against *Cryptococcus neoformans* (MIC = 4.15 µg/mL). YM-202204 (**56**) showed broad-spectrum activity, displaying high efficacy against azole-resistant *A. fumigatus* (MIC = 0.52 µg/mL) and *M. plumbeus* (MIC = 1.04 µg/mL), and moderate activity against *C. albicans* (MIC = 8.3 µg/mL) and *A. fumigatus* (MIC = 8.3 µg/mL). Dactylfungin C (**58**) had a significant impact on the growth of *A. fumigatus* (MIC = 0.26 µg/mL) but showed weak activity against azole-resistant *A. fumigatus* (MIC = 16.6 µg/mL). Additionally, three tetralone derivatives were identified: laburnicolin (**59**), laburnicolenone (**60**), and the previously described 10-norparvulenone (**61**). Beside the dactylfungins the identified metabolites (**49** – **54**, **59** – **61**) showed no significant activities against the tested organisms and cell lines.

Ongoing studies on the secondary metabolites from *L. nematophila* have led to the isolation of vancouverone A (**62**) and B (**63**), along with three potential new derivatives. These compounds, based on their structural similarity to newly described tenellin derivatives by Toshe et al. (2024), are being investigated for biofilm inhibition and disruption properties, as well as antimicrobial, cytotoxic, and nematocidal properties [Toshe et al., 2024]. Additionally, the production of eight different cordypyridones, including six potentially new derivatives and the known derivatives C (**64**) and D (**65**), was discovered and is currently under investigation for their effects in various bioassays.

The strains of *L. nematophila* demonstrated a dual lifestyle as nematophagous and endophytic fungi, highlighting their potential to produce a diverse array of novel metabolites. Notably, the dactylfungins, characterised by an alpha-pyrone motif bridged to a polyalcohol with an aliphatic

side chain, have shown potent antifungal and antiviral properties. Dactylfungin D, patented under S39163/FI, has demonstrated activity against herpes viruses and notable antifungal efficacy against *A. fumigatus* [Tscherter et al., 1988]. YM-202204 has been reported to possess antifungal activities against *Candida albicans*, *C. neoformans*, and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* [Nagai et al., 2003]. The findings from this study, along with data from related compounds such as fusapyrones and other dactylfungin congeners, suggest a correlation between increased efficacy and greater hydrophobicity of the side chain [Charria-Girón et al., 2023].

Figure 3.2. Metabolites isolated from *Laburnicola nematophila*

The study of Ashrafi et al. 2023 (publication VI) focused on six strains isolated from the eggs of the cereal cyst nematode *Heterodera filipjevi* and the roots of *Microthlaspi perfoliatum*. These fungi exhibit a dual lifestyle, acting both as parasite of *H. filipjevi* eggs and as plant root endophytes, showing similarities to the previously mentioned species *L. nematophila* and *P. sieberi* [Ashrafi et al., 2018; Knapp et al., 2022]. Phylogenetic analyses have positioned the newly introduced species *P. karssenii* within a monophyletic group with high statistical support within the Phaeosphaeriaceae family, exhibiting a close evolutionary relationship with *Equiseticola* and *Ophiosphaerella*. The isolated fungal strains showed similar growth characteristics but varied in morphological traits. Metabolite profiling of six *P. karssenii* strains cultivated in three different media revealed the presence of several metabolites, including the nematicidal ophiotine (**32**) and xanthomide Z (**66**), beside arthrichitin (**67**), and arthrichitin B (**68**), as described previously [Helaly et al., 2018] beside other unknown compounds. Their LC-MS profiles show high similarity between the different studied isolates. Notably, two metabolites were produced exclusively in endophytic isolates. Preliminary data from follow-up investigations on the strains 5BD (DSM 111209) and P2789 (JKI 73120) indicate the presence of different cyclodepsipeptides like compound (**69**) and undescribed *cis*-decalin tetramic acids (**70 – 74**). These metabolites are right in the process of determining their absolute configuration and are tested for their effect on different microorganisms. The initial findings indicate that the tetramic acids (**72 – 73**) are effective against *C. elegans*. Furthermore the impact on the beet cyst nematode (*Heterodera schachtii*) will be evaluated.

From the nematode-derived fungus *Pochonia chlamydosporia* (66T), the main metabolite compound (**75**) isolated from liquid Q6/2 media cultures initially peaked interest due to its antiplasmodial activities. The metabolite later also showed to possess highly cytotoxic and nematicidal properties. This compound shares the same core structure as the insecticidal PF1018 described before [Gomi et al., 1994]. Motivated by the dominant cytotoxicity of the PF1018 derivative, this compound is the process of further evaluation by Katharin Schmidt (ZBIO, HZI) for its effects on cells and the actin network. Additionally, minor produced metabolites of *P. chlamydosporia* were identified as previously described monocillins.

Figure 3.2. Metabolites produced by *Polydomus karsseni* (32, 66 – 74) and *Pochonia chlamydosporia* 66T (75)

In conclusion, the metabolites produced by nematophagous fungi represent a diverse and potent arsenal against several pathogens. It is therefore vital that continued research and development in this field be pursued in order to fully harness their potential and integrate them into modern applications. This will provide a sustainable solution for global challenges.

The importance of researching potent antifungals, such as dactylfungins, lies in addressing the major issue of multidrug-resistant fungi—a problem that, compared to multidrug-resistant bacteria, is often overlooked [Hyde et al., 2018]. This issue is worsened by the limited variety of

compounds available for treating fungal infections [Mapook et al., 2022]. The World Health Organization (WHO) has identified fungal species such as *Cryptococcus neoformans*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, and *Candida* spp. in the critical priority group, underscoring the urgent need to develop novel strategies to combat these pathogens [World Health Organization, 2022]. The situation is made even worse by the extensive use of fungicides, particularly of the azole-type, in agriculture, which contributes to the increasing prevalence of resistant strains [Berger et al., 2017; Cao et al., 2021]. The impact of fungal pathogens in agriculture is significantly greater than that of bacterial pathogens, intensifying the demand for new antimycotics to ensure both the stability of agricultural yields and the effective treatment of fungal infections [Verweij et al., 2020; Mapook et al., 2022].

A significant proportion of compounds in this work could not be tested in all available bioassays due to low yields caused by low metabolite production titers. Historical examples such as pleuromutilin, illustrates the challenges in developing fungal lead compounds into marketed drugs due to low production titers. Pleuromutilin, for instance, lacked an efficient production process, delaying its development into the semisynthetic derivative, retapamulin. This issue highlights a significant obstacle in this thesis as well as in natural product research: the low yields of isolated natural products. Innovative biotechnological and metabolomics techniques are necessary to enhance the yield of these compounds and access the full diversity of natural products produced by fungi. Once production is increased, these metabolites can be submitted to screening libraries to evaluate a wide range of potential targets. Subsequent chemical modifications can then be applied to significantly enhance the efficacy of these lead compounds. Historical examples demonstrate that many compounds initially discovered in antibiotic screening programs were later found to possess additional biological properties, enabling their use in various fields [Karwehl and Stadler, 2016].

Returning to the motivation for this thesis, which seeks to explore the chemical diversity of natural products produced by nematophagous fungi to find new antimicrobial agents. The present research demonstrates that egg-parasitizing fungi offer a promising source of novel natural products. Ongoing metabolite profiling of these newly described fungi has identified several metabolites with significant biological activity. Compounds with unknown functions could

play crucial roles in the multifunctional lifestyle of these fungi, potentially mediating interactions among plants, fungi, and nematodes. Several hypotheses explain why these metabolites are produced: they may help fight competitors, improve plant health or growth by mitigating abiotic or biotic stress or production of phytohormones, or serve as communication molecules within or between species [Rodriguez et al., 2009; Rai et al., 2021]. The synthesis of secondary metabolites by these organisms suggests that they provide some benefit, as these compounds would not be produced otherwise [Keller et al., 2011].

In summary there is still a lot of to discover as many geographic regions have not been thoroughly investigated for nematode antagonistic fungi, which could provide a variety of different fungal species with potential nematode suppressing properties and/or as producers of diversity of unique natural products.

4. Conclusion

This thesis has unveiled bioactive compounds with potential for follow-up studies. Despite this success, the scope of screening organisms and other possible targets in this study has been relatively limited. Nevertheless, further bioactivity testing is necessary, particularly for the metabolites showing significant activity or no activities. All compounds with sufficient yield were included in a screening program at the Helmholtz Institute for Pharmaceutical Research in Saarbrücken (HIPS).

Furthermore, this thesis emphasises the significant potential of fungi as a source of novel natural products. In conclusion, the genus *Polyphilus* is a notable source of mycotoxins, including talaroderxine C and D, as well as other intriguing metabolites. While these properties highlight *Polyphilus* as a valuable source of natural products, they also restrict its potential as a biocontrol agent due to the production of toxic compounds. The findings indicate that both *L. nematophila* and *P. karssenii* are robust producers of secondary metabolites with a wide range of chemical structures. Notably, *P. karssenii* synthesizes not only the previously identified nematicidal compounds ophiotine and xanthomide Z but also novel tetramic acids. These newly discovered tetramic acids exhibit lethal effects on nematodes, potentially enhancing the fungus's ability to effectively kill nematodes while parasitizing their eggs. Preliminary results indicate that there are

still some secondary metabolites that have yet to be discovered and characterised. Thus far, the conducted bioassays have not raised concerns about developing them into biocontrol strategies.

This work underscores the importance of conducting a thorough evaluation of these fungi and their produced metabolites before further development for agricultural applications as biocontrol agents. As demonstrated by the isolation of highly cytotoxic talaroderxine C and D from *Polyphilus sieberi*, this process is necessary to identify producers of potential detrimental mycotoxins, which could cause environmental harm.

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- This research benefitted from funding by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (RISE) under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 101008129, project acronym "Mycobiomics".

**Funded by
the European Union**

